

A TEACHER WHO SPEAKS WISE WORDS

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Abstract. *This article is devoted to the topic of reading Hamid Olimjon's works for children. In particular, we are talking about fairy tales. Folktales are usually rooted in folklore. Hamid Olimjon's fairy tales are written in poetic, fluent language and are distinguished by their unique and interesting plots. Fairy tales, especially their poetic forms, play an important role in the formation of children's imaginations and thoughts. Expands worldview, increases creative abilities.*

Keywords: *literary tale, folklore, images, imagery, simile, metaphor.*

The word. Its magic and light have been a guiding star illuminating the path of humanity. He paints people's visions of the world from childhood. But what about artistic expression? The artistic word is embodied like a wise teacher who draws us like a steel rod from childhood and instills the fundamentals of spiritual and moral education without realizing it. A fairy tale is one of the first educators of children. It leads to goodness. The Dalai Lama said about this: "A person who believes in a fairy tale will one day fall into a fairy tale himself, because he has a good heart".

Hamid Olimjon's beautiful literary tales are a clear example of this. It is no exaggeration to say that every child of our country grew up with the pleasant tone of these fairy tales and the development of interesting and instructive events. Every poet and writer who writes for adults has a work written for children.

Yes, children's creators are considered mentors who speak this wise word. Although Hamid Olimjon's work is mainly aimed at a large audience of readers, several of his poems and fairy tales have taken a worthy place in Uzbek children's literature.

In fact, a literary fairy tale serves the same task as a folklore example - to develop figurative thinking, an active life position and creative ability in children, to expand their worldview, to find answers to the questions of what is good and what is bad, and helps to think about the positive and negative characteristics of a person.

It is natural that it should be so. After all, poets and writers who create for children have great possibilities of fantasy. Raised by his mother - Komila aya and grandfather - Mulla Azim, who was fond of literature, Hamid Olimjon grew up listening to folktales and epics of Fazil Bakhshi, which were examples of folk oral creativity, which motivated him to write literary tales. It is this attractive effect that is reflected in the reworking of the Uzbek folk tale "Princess Husnabad" by H.Olimjon.

In my childhood days,
In my sleepless nights,
I heard many tales
Grandma used to talk.
...Every story of my grandmother
Every contribution
It was distracting me,

I was anxious.

While describing the pleasure he got from Uzbek folk tales and their heroes in this tale, the poet remembers flying carpets, Tahir-Zuhra, Yoriltash, grass-covered wings and wildly flying horses. As mentioned above, because Hamid Olimjon was familiar with folk tales and epics, as well as A. Pushkin's tales, he wrote "Oygul and Bakhtiyar" not only reworks the fairy tale based on an interesting plot, but also presents it to children in an interesting way.

Because of this, it is no coincidence that the work is included in the golden fund of Uzbek children's literature. Pushkin's "Ruslan and Lyudmila" the first song of the fairy-tale and the introduction of H. Olimjon's fairy tale "Oygul bilan Bakhtiyor", although different from each other, remind the reader of a general interesting explanation before taking the reader on a journey to the world of fairy tales.

“Near the sea there is a green oak,
Golden chain on the oak tree... – A.S.Pushkin begins his first song and continues:
There on unknown paths
Traces of unseen beasts,
There's a hut there on chicken legs
It stands without windows, without doors.
In the dungeon there the princess is grieving,
And the brown wolf serves her faithfully.
There is a stupa with Baba Yaga,
It walks and wanders by itself.
There King Kasha is wasting away over his gold,
There's a Russian spirit there, it smells like Russia.

In every line of H. Olimjon's fairy tales, the influence of nationalism and folklore is extremely strong, just like in Pushkin's fairy tales. But H. Olimjon brings his heroes closer to the people.

In folk tales, she is the daughter of Husnabad-shah, and in Hamid Olimjon's fairy tale, Aigul is the daughter of the slave Tarkhan. The slaves who could not bear the tyranny of the king rebelled. Their leader was Aigul's father. But the servants of the king cruelly suppress the rebellion of the slaves and take the surviving Tarkhan and Aigul to the king.

Husnabad's character is more resentful of her mother, while Aigul's character is a girl oppressed by the enslavement and helpless condition of her people. After all, Aigul himself is a representative of this oppressed people.

The murder of Tarkhan's father in front of Aigul's eyes causes revenge for the girl. And to do that, he had to survive himself.

Aigul, who did not agree to marry the king, is rescued by her father's friend and put in a chest. First, the shepherd boy Aigul, who survived because he fell into the hands of another king and won a miracle - a fish, falls into the hands of Bakhtiyar and his father. The girl sells the gems she found in the belly of the fish and starts a big construction. It attracts many poor families to the construction and provides them with food. He wants to create a new world in Susambil. He expresses his dreams in the following lines:

We are new at Susanbil
We want to build a world
Every poor helper
Be our faithful guardian.

Only such a country
 The oppressed build
 Then they layer by layer,
 They live in houses.

Aigul "What did he give to whom?" This is how the poet answers the question.
 To whom? What gave?

To those who work	food
For not alive	alive
To the orphans	care
For orphans	Trust and work
For children	palaces, beautiful, neat places
For people	garden
everywhere	hot spring

In these lands of majestic and Aigul's dream, suckling pigs were cooked on wood fires, and children's heads were grown in flower gardens. Of course, the exaggeration characteristic of fairy tales creates an opportunity to make the author's literary fairy tale more expressive and interesting. In describing the beauty of Aigul, comparisons, similes, and folk expressions characteristic of fairy tales are used.

The moon has a face
 He has an eye when he says day.
 Beautiful, wise Aigul,
 This is a spring flower
 He loved dearly.

The example of Aigul is that a flower blooms, and when he meets the khan, who gives him a day's respite, he "tears like a comb" with his wise words. Aigul heads to Jambil to take revenge on the khan who killed his father and enslaved the people. H. Olimjon describes the way of Aigul towards Jambil as follows.

This journey begins with trumpets. Because this war seeks justice for the people and the truth. That is why Aigul's journey becomes a holiday. At the head of the army he goes on the road.
 This is how Hamid Olimjon describes them.

Of course, every fairy tale should have a good ending. In this tale by Hamid Olimjon, Aigul wins and leads Tarlan to his motherland.

Justice is another "Semurg' or Parizod and Bunyod" author also finds a solution in the fairy tale. Because intelligence and value are the best, the scheming and oppressive Parizod was not at all worthy of Bunyod. From the beginning of the tale, we get a good impression of Parizod.

A beautiful fairy
Grew free from sorrows,
Spring has just opened,
Scattered like flowers.

Although the rumor about Parizod's beauty is everywhere, the girl will not agree to any of the suitors. He gradually gets a bad name among the people. The king regrets this situation and his daughter. He calls his daughter and asks him to please someone. Then Parizod comes up with a condition for the groom candidates. The condition is as follows: if someone knocks down a hundred-year-old maple tree in the yard, he agrees to touch it. Unfortunately, because of this condition, many young men lost their lives, others' backs were broken, many leeches fell down and became lame. But not a branch of the sycamore is broken. When the king wants to know who else in the country has not passed the test, he is told that there is a young shepherd named Bunyod. The king says that they will bring him and even give his own horse to Bunyod. Although Bunyod fulfills the condition, Parizod cunningly prepares another condition for him. It was to defeat the Giant on the sunny side. The ideal hero of the epic, the warrior Bunyod, certainly rides to fulfill this condition. On the way, the bird takes him to Giant's place for saving Semurg's children from the snake. But the bird reveals another secret to Bunyod. Parizod and Giant are friends with each other. Licking snake oil, Parizod sends his men whom he hates and wants to put to death to Giant. Even after hearing these words, the brave and brave Bunyod does not turn back from his path. The author describes the Terrible Giant as follows:

Bunyod wins over such a powerful creature. But when he came to Parizod, he was awaited by the trick of the unfaithful friend. Parizod meets Bunyod with a son and a daughter. After all, she married her father's minister as soon as Bunyod left.

Although the tale does not end with Bunyod reaching Parizod, it finds a happy ending in the hearts of the readers. Because for Bunyod, the most loyal and virtuous man is worthy. Both of the above-mentioned fairy tales of H. Olimjon teach children to distinguish between good and bad, positive and negative qualities and characteristics in people and to absorb the best. It teaches that loyalty, kindness, good will never remain on earth, and evil will be punished one day at a time. It proves that wealth does not bring happiness to everyone, that a person's dedication to creative work, entering into work with good dreams and taking care of others will ensure his success in his work.

H. A number of Olimjon's poems can also be recommended for children's literature. This is his "Uzbekistan" and other poems.

His poem "Uzbekistan" is imbued with the spirit of great patriotism, and this patriotism embodies the beautiful beauty of our country and the works of people in it in pleasant, beautiful, natural and sincere verses.

When wandering the valleys
 I had a strange feeling.
 A garden that bloomed with clapper,
 I was kissing the soil of my country.
 Listening to stories from people,
 An idea was growing in the poet.

From the beginning of the poem, you will feel as if you are listening to the words of the poet, who wants to travel through Uzbekistan - his motherland, to get acquainted with its today, its vibrant life. He is crossing rivers singing, he is listening to fairy tales. He is listening to everyone, watching everyone around. But he does not find anything similar to the country he is looking at. Let's put Uzbekistan in the cluster described by H.Olimjon.

As the poet continues his poem, he animates all animate and inanimate, even abstract phenomena in his country. Writes what makes people.

Here:	
Who, what	What to do?
nightingale	Read a book
worms	weaves silk
bee	brings a honey
birds	luck will find
winter	applause speaks for spring
day	works on cotton every day
braves	digs a canal
poets	Writes gazal
singers	Reads yalla
girls	Speaks yalla
cookers	Make a bread
olders	the guest is waiting

This poem of Hamid Olimjon can be called an ode filled with feelings and emotions about his country. It is natural that in the heart of every young generation who read the poem, it arouses infinite pride for their country. Despite the fact that the work was written a long time ago, it expresses the mentality of the people and the beauty of our country as if it were today. The comparison of the image of nature used in the poem brings it to life before the eyes of the reader.

The crimson tulip in the mountains,
 Like a ruby cup
 Water flows from springs.

A.Oripov says about H.Olimjon: "There are certainly the most beautiful and elegant examples of lyrics in Uzbek poetry. But the lyrics of Hamid Olimjon are not like the lyrics of any other poet. These lyrics are crystal clear, but not dull. In it, both the image and the tone are fragmentary.

Another reason why the poem, which is full of beautiful allusions and animations, has taken a stronger place than children's literature, is that it is typical of children's poetry. K.Chukovsky says in his rules of writing poems for children: 1. "Written poems should be descriptive, because children have the ability to think figuratively. It is necessary to think with pictures, the child should

see what is happening while reading the poem. If after writing a page you only need to draw one picture on it, delete it as invalid.

2. Rapid exchange of images. Cinematographic images should be exchanged with each other like frames in a movie;

3. The image in the word should be poetic.

4. Emotionality and mobility of rhythm;

5. Extreme musicality of the poem".

As we can see, Hamid Olimjon's children's works meet all these requirements.

Although the poet had a short life, he achieved a worthy place not only in adult literature, but also in children's literature with his immortal works. As a singer of happiness and joy, among his many works, he left the poem "Uzbekistan" that instills the feeling of love for his country and infinite pride in the future generation. And his fairy tales continue to instill the most beautiful qualities in young readers.

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